

PHRASES AND IDIOMS RELATED TO MEDICINE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10902852>

Abstract. *In this article, we can look at medical terms and expressions, different types of health problems in patients and their treatment methods.*

Key words: *medicine, treatment, patient, common health problems, types of diseases, medical procedures, medical idioms.*

ФРАЗЫ И ИДИОМЫ, СВЯЗАННЫЕ С МЕДИЦИНОЙ

Аннотация. *в этой статье мы можем рассмотреть медицинские термины и выражения, различные виды проблем со здоровьем у пациентов и методы их лечения*

Ключевые слова: *медицина, лечение, пациент, распространенные проблемы со здоровьем, виды заболеваний, медицинские процедуры, медицинские идиомы.*

Medicine is the science and practice of caring for a patient, managing the diagnosis, prognosis, prevention, treatment, palliation of their injury or disease, and promoting their health. Medicine encompasses a variety of health care practices evolved to maintain and restore health by the prevention and treatment of illness. Contemporary medicine applies biomedical sciences, biomedical research, genetics, and medical technology to diagnose, treat, and prevent injury and disease, typically through pharmaceuticals or surgery, but also through therapies as diverse as psychotherapy, external splints and traction, medical devices, biologics, and ionizing radiation, amongst others.

Medical availability and clinical practice vary across the world due to regional differences in culture and technology. Modern scientific medicine is highly developed in the Western world, while in developing countries such as parts of Africa or Asia, the population may rely more heavily on traditional medicine with limited evidence and efficacy and no required formal training for practitioners.

In the developed world, evidence-based medicine is not universally used in clinical practice; for example, a 2007 survey of literature reviews found that about 49% of the interventions lacked sufficient evidence to support either benefit or harm.

Common health problems

Recognizing common ailments and their symptoms can be crucial for your well-being. Below, you'll find a list of frequent illnesses, along with brief descriptions to assist you in identifying and communicating them.

- Fever – isitma: an abnormally high body temperature; often a sign of infection.
- Cough – yo'tal: a sudden expulsion of air from the lungs; usually caused by illness.
- Allergy – allergiya: a response from the immune system (red eyes, runny nose, skin irritation) usually to a certain food, medicine, material, or smell.
- Infection – infeksiya: invasion and multiplication of microorganisms; such as bacteria, viruses, etc.
- Asthma – astma(nafas olish bilan bog'liq): a respiratory condition that causes difficulty in breathing.
- Diabetes – diabet: a chronic condition that affects the body's ability to use sugar.
- Migraine – migren**9**boshni qattiq og'ritadigan va ko'ngilni aynitib, ko'rishni xiralashtiradigan kasallik): a type of headache.
- Anxiety – bezovtalik: a mental health disorder that causes excessive fear and worry.
- Depression – depressiya: a mental health condition that leads to persistent sadness and loss of interest.
- Arthritis – bo'g'im yallig'lanishi: the problem of one or more body parts' joints that causes pain and stiffness.
- Fracture – sinish: a break in a bone; requires medical attention.
- Flu – gripp: an infectious disease caused by a virus; symptoms include fever and cough.
- Indigestion – ovqat hazm bo'lmasligi natijasida paydo bo'ladigan og'riq: discomfort in the stomach; often after eating.
- Hypertension – qon bosimini normal holatdan yuqoribo'lishi: also known as high blood pressure; can lead to serious health problems.

Familiarity with these ailments will enable you to describe symptoms more precisely and understand medical advice. Keep this medical vocabulary in mind, as they are essential for everyday health-related communication.

Medical Procedures

Medical procedures play a crucial role in maintaining and restoring health. However, the medical vocabulary used to describe these procedures can be confusing. In the following section, you'll find a detailed list of terms related to examinations and treatments designed to demystify medical processes and help you communicate more effectively with healthcare providers.

Examinations

Medical examinations are vital for diagnosing and monitoring health conditions. Here, you'll learn about different tests and procedures that doctors may use to assess your health.

- ❖ Check-up - tekshirish: a general examination by a doctor; often for routine health assessment.
- ❖ X-ray: a type of imaging test; uses radiation to view inside the body.
- ❖ Blood test – qon analizi: laboratory analysis of a blood sample; used to check various health conditions.
- ❖ Biopsy: the removal and examination of body cells, liquid, or tissue to diagnose a condition.
- ❖ MRI scan: an imaging test; uses magnetic fields to create detailed images of the body.
- ❖ Ultrasound: a diagnostic tool; uses sound waves to view internal organs.
- ❖ CT scan: a type of X-ray; provides cross-sectional images of the body.
- ❖ Eye exam: an evaluation of vision and eye health; performed by an optometrist.
- ❖ Physical therapy: a treatment plan; helps restore movement and reduce pain.
- ❖ Dental exam: a check-up of teeth and gums; performed by a dentist.
- ❖ ECG: a test that records heart activity; detects heart problems.
- ❖ Urine test: an analysis of a urine sample; checks for kidney problems or infections.

Having a clear understanding of these examination terms will help you know what to expect during medical appointments. They'll also enable you to communicate effectively with healthcare professionals about your health status.

Treatments

Medical treatments vary widely and may involve medications, therapies, or surgeries. This section will introduce you to terms related to various treatments that you might encounter.

- Surgery: a medical procedure used to repair or remove parts of the body.

- Therapy: treatment to relieve or heal a disorder.
- Medication: a substance used to treat an illness or condition; often prescribed by a doctor.
- Vaccination: administration of a vaccine; helps the body develop immunity to a disease.
- Chemotherapy: a cancer treatment; uses drugs to kill or slow the growth of cancer cells.
- Radiation therapy: a cancer treatment; uses high-energy radiation to kill cancer cells.
- Dialysis: a treatment for kidney failure; removes waste products from the blood.
- Insulin therapy: a treatment for diabetes; controls blood sugar levels.
- Antibiotics: medications that fight infections; usually for bacterial infections.
- Immunotherapy: a treatment that boosts the immune system; often for cancer patients.
- Transplant: replacing a failing organ with a healthy one from a donor.
- Physical rehabilitation: a program to restore strength and mobility after injury or surgery.
- Inhaler: a device delivering medication often used for asthma.
- Acupuncture: a traditional Chinese therapy; uses needles to stimulate specific points.

By knowing these treatment-related terms, you'll gain a better understanding of medical care options. This knowledge will allow you to engage more confidently in discussions in English for medicine and treatment.

Medical idioms

Go under the knife – means undergoing surgery

A taste of your own medicine – experience the same unpleasant or harmful treatment that one has given to others.

At death's door – to be close to death

Just what the Dr ordered – exactly what is wanted or needed to Improve the situation/condition

Take a turn for the worse – to get worse (sicker) often suddenly

On the mend – healing and becoming well again

Headstart – an advantage over everyone else

Gut feeling – sense of impression that your subconscious is working on someone or some situation

Joined at the hip – to be exceptionally close to someone

Find your feet – to adjust to a new place or situation

Hands are tied – you are prevented from doing something, or it is not within your power

As pale as a ghost – Extremely pale

A bitter pill to swallow – An unpleasant fact that one must accept

Have one foot in the grave – To be near death

Under the weather – not feeling well.

Sick and tired of -Extremely annoyed by something that occurs repeatedly

Forty winks – short naps

On its last legs – near the end of life

Out of sorts – a little unwell

Black and Blue – badly bruised

Alive and Kicking – In good health despite health problems

On the back burner – It's not a priority

It's not rocket science – which means it's easy

I will stick an IV – will insert an IV

What a “hard stick!” – means difficult veins

Crunching the numbers- means doing a lot of calculations.

Put something off – put in a delay

Call the shots – to make major decisions

Slacking off – working lazily

Have a lot on your plate -Have a lot of responsibilities

Learning curve - the rate of gaining experience or new skills

24/7 – 24 hours a day, seven days a week

I'm buckling down – I am focusing and putting a lot of energy into a project

She goes the extra mile – She does more than expected

Work in progress – work continues

To work something out – to find a solution to a problem

Shift work – work at different times of the day

Carry out the task – complete the order

Called off – canceled

Propped up bed – elevated head of the bed

By knowing these treatment-related terms and idioms, you'll gain a better understanding of medical care options. This knowledge will allow you to engage more confidently in discussions in English for medicine and treatment.

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